

PRINCIPALS' LEADERSHIP STRATEGIES AND THEIR IMPLICATIONS FOR TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE.

By

USMAN SHOLA RAHEEM

and

ABDULKAREEM A. MUSA

Dept. Of CSET School of Education, COED, Ilorin.

Abstract

This paper examined the school principal leadership strategies and their implications on teachers' job performance. The concept of leadership and principal behaviour were extensively explained. The various leadership strategies which include Teacher/Personnel management strategy, student management strategy and resources management strategy were dealt with. The implications of principal leadership strategies on teachers' job performance were not left out while recommendations were made on the ways through which the principal can enhance his teachers Job performance through an effective leadership strategies.

Introduction

Educationists recognize the importance of leadership in any educational system. This is why over the years educationists have concerned themselves with studies on leadership as a concept in relation to teachers' responsibility within the school environment and student's academic performance.

The school principal as a leader plays his management roles through artful application of techniques and implementation of educational programmes towards the realization of the school objectives. In actual fact the smooth operation of the school setting depends on efficient and effective leadership. Hence, a school leader

will be effective through the application of some leadership strategies.

Moreover, in any organization such as the school setting, Principals' administration is aimed at complementing teachers' job performance to achieve pre-determined goals. However, leadership strategies of school principals could have some remarkable implications on teachers' job performance in any school setting.

It is therefore the responsibility of the school principal to ensure that he has adequate knowledge of his staff in terms of their ability, temperament, interest etc. so as to adopt an appropriate leadership strategy that will enhance the smooth running of the school.

Concept of Leadership

There are many ways of looking at leadership and many interpretations of its meaning. Ogunu (2000), defined leadership as a “dynamic process in a group whereby an individual influences the other to contribute voluntarily to achievement of group tasks in a given situation”. Kenneth (2006), defined leadership as a process by which a person influences others to accomplish an objective and direct the organization in a way that makes it more cohesive and coherent. Leaders, according to Kenneth (2006), carry out this process by applying their leadership attributes such as beliefs, values, ethics, character, knowledge and skills.

Boje (2000), defined leadership as the effort to influence the behaviour of individual or group members in order to accomplish organizational, individual or personal goals. It is an essential component of organizational effectiveness. Bass (1990), saw leadership as a process that shapes the goals of a group or organization, motives and behaviours toward the achievement of those goals and helps define group or organization culture. Okorie (2002), quoting Adesina (1990), defined leadership as the activity of influencing people to strive willingly for goals.

This definition, according to Okorie (2002) implies that it is vital for school heads who are usually leaders of their schools to have the ability to inspire or get all members of the school community to work together toward the goal of excellent

education for all students.

Generally, leadership as being defined by many authors centered on behaviour modification, therefore leadership can be seen as the effort to influence the behaviour of individuals or group members in order to accomplish organizational, individual or personal goals.

Principal Leadership Behaviour

In a school setting, the responsibility of the principal is to facilitate and promote teaching and learning process in order to achieve desired goals of the school. Sanni (1999), noted that the attention of the principal must be drawn to the fact that for the aims and objectives of the school to be achieved, each member of staff must act professionally and work hard for the good of the school. For the school principal to succeed in advertising these, he must display a kind of behaviour that will elicit the cooperation of his staff such that will lead to the accomplishment of the school goals. He (principal) should have a good vision, good communication skills and ability to evaluate situation carefully before taking action. All these behaviours exhibited by the principal demonstrate an effective leadership that would lead the school to perform better academically.

Blanchard and Hersey (1993) characterized leadership behaviour in terms of the amount of direction and support that a leader gives to his followers, and so created a simple grid. The supportive behaviour is on the vertical axis while the directive behaviour is on the horizontal axis as shown in figure 1 below

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SUPPORTIVE BEHAVIOUR	SUPPORTING (S3) COACTING (S2)
	DELEGATING (S4) DIRECTING (S1)

Directive behaviour

Source: Blanchard and Hersey 1993. Management of organizational behaviour.

SI Directing Leaders: This is not different from the traditional leader approach.

Directing leaders define the roles and tasks for the followers and supervise them closely. Decisions are made by the leader and announced, so communication is largely one-way.

S2. Coaching leaders still define roles and tasks but seek ideas and suggestions from the follower. Decision remains the leader's prerogative but communication is much more two-way.

S3. Supporting leaders pass day-to-day decisions such as task allocation and process to the follower. The leader facilitates and takes part in decision, but control is with the follower.

S4. Delegating leader is still involved in decision and problem solving but control is with the follower. The follower decides when and how the leader will be involved.

Effective leaders are versatile in being able to move round the grid according to the situation so there is no one right behaviour. Leadership behaviour will, however, depend very much on the type of people being led.

Transformational Leadership in School Setting

It is observed that our school system needs a change of attitude and values in order to meet the challenges of the modern society. There is equally a need to restructure our educational system to become a better place for teaching and learning where educational goals can be achieved. This demands for better leadership strategies such that will bring out the best of teachers whereby educational goals could be achieved.

There are different types of leadership styles ranging from laissez-faire, democratic or participative, autocratic, benevolent etc. Each of these leadership strategies possesses positive and negative effect depending on the situation on ground. However, Barueff and Conuers (2001), argued that transformational forms of leadership are well suited to such challenges of our educational system because of their potential to bring about the changes demanded from our schools, and for building motivation, commitment and developing capable teachers whom we need to overcome the challenges associated with the restructuring exercise.

Furthermore, they believe that transformational leadership behaviours are concerned with setting directions, developing people, organizing and building relationship with the school community. They argued that transformational approaches to leadership are increasingly advocated for schools as they continue to face the challenges of schools restructuring.

Principals' Leadership Strategies

The principal is the key person in the day to day administration and organization of a school setting. He deals with people with specific intention of achieving the institutional goal. He requires planning, organizing, coordinating and evaluating the total institutional system in line with the desired objectives.

Within the policy units and guidelines of the school system, the principal should work towards the attainment of educational goals. Hence, in an attempt to promote various activities of the school, the principal needs to adopt some leadership

strategies for the proper running of the school. These, among others, include:

Teacher/Personnel Management Strategy: This is an effort of the school principal directed towards human resources within the school in order to get their maximum cooperation towards getting the work done effectively. Having realized that he (Principal) can not get all the school works done, there is a need for delegation of authority.

Ama (2004), noted that an effective managerial practice will create good school climate, reduce chaos, frustration, threatening of principals' leadership position and inefficiency and equally encourages initiatives, bring about a better learning environment and achievement of school objectives.

Furthermore, the principal should involve his subordinates in the decision making and he should exhibit a kind of human relation technique that will ensure a cooperative relationship among his subordinates. Good human relations on the part of the principal will definitely help to secure a tension free, positive and effective climate in which the teacher feels free to operate. In making decision, the principal should ensure full participation of his subordinates.

Lampere (2004) opined that decision making among teachers should involve mutual relationship in which every one of them, from junior teachers to senior ones would have the opportunity to comment on every policy suggestions and raise issues of concern.

Resources Management Strategy: The school principal has a lot of resources at his disposal and these should be systematically and judiciously utilized to achieve the goals of the school. These resources include, among others, the school plant, school facilities and equipment, materials available for use in school as well as monetary resources available. The principal should ensure that the school plants are well maintained so as to this will facilitate effective teaching and learning. Ogunu (2000), sees school facilities as those things of education which enables a skillful teacher to achieve a level of instruction effectiveness that are not provided.

More so, the school principal should be aware of the financial control mechanism such as auditing methods, financial regulations and other government circulars on school expenditure. These should guide the opening and operation of various school revenue and expenditure account books. It is the duty of the principal to ensure that the available resources are within the reach of the users. Both the teachers should have equal access to them and they should be rationally distributed.

Student/Personnel Management Strategy: students are part of the resources available to a school principal whom he has to manage for effective teaching and learning to take place. The school principal should ensure effective supervision and monitoring of students' activities in a school setting to ensure that they conform to generally accepted principles and practice of education. He should also ensure conformity with the stipulated policies and guidelines of the education authority which controls the system of education. Furthermore, the school principal should maintain cordial relationship with the community and the public where school is located. This is an indirect way of developing a positive school image and climate since the community is involved in various school activities and decision making processes.

A good understanding of the school beliefs and values becomes imperative for the establishment of good working relationship among colleagues. Hence, the principal should develop a shared belief and values. This will no doubt lead to the creation of common vision towards which every member of staff will be working. This will be a joint and exemplary venture for the school.

Implications of Principals' Leadership Strategies on Teachers' Job Performance

Attempts to improve the general tone of the school has led various principals to adopt different administrative policies, each of which have measurable effects, both positively and negatively, on teachers' job performance. School principals should be aware of the fact that both internal and external environmental factors

affect their leadership strategies. Therefore, they should adjust their leadership strategies to make it relevant and also to assist the school towards positive outcome. A well designed school programme with adequate resources at teachers' disposal may be rendered useless if the leadership strategy is ineffective.

It is worth mentioning here that a fundamental mechanism for effective leadership in schools is healthy relationship with individual members of the school community. Barnett (2001), believes that leadership in schools is mainly characterized by relationship with individuals, and it is through these relationships that principals are able to establish leadership control and encourage teachers to apply their abilities, skills and efforts toward shared purposes. These will consequently enhance their job performance.

The principal should as well give his subordinates the authority needed to perform their duties without constantly referring decision to himself unnecessarily. He should be tactful and firm in decision making sure as all these will definitely enhance teachers' job performance.

It is also the duty of the school principal to initiate new structures and procedures so that the goals of the school will be better achieved. He should use power, personal attributes and experience to direct and coordinate the activities of the subordinates so as to attain success.

Communication is important in any formal organization, therefore the school head or principal should ensure that information flow freely from an appropriate source to the right destination. All forms of communication barriers should be avoided in order to prevent chaos and to create sense of belongingness in every member of the school community. This will surely improve teachers' commitment and enhance their job performance.

Conclusion

It is crystal clear that effective leadership strategy is a necessary requirement for good organizational climate, sense of direction towards goal, sense of belonging

and quality work.

Furthermore, effective leadership strategy could evoke patriotism, loyalty, harmony, commitment and enhancement of teachers' job performance which would lead to high productivity and attainment of the desired educational goals. The school principal should have it at the back of his mind that his leadership strategy could make or mar teachers' job performance depending on the leadership style.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are hereby made:

- The school principal should realize that no particular perfect leadership strategy, but the situation on ground will determine the leadership strategy to be adopted. Hence the principal should adopt the leadership strategy that suits the prevailing condition.
- There should be an induction programme and seminars as well as workshop for school principals in order to enhance their service delivery.
- There should also be a leadership evaluation annual report to be provided and completed by teachers and students in order to assess the leadership effectiveness of the principal.

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